

Fractional derivatives of composite functions via an extension of Bell exponential polynomials

Giuseppe Tavazza, Milano, Italy

Address for correspondence: giuseppe.tavazza@fastwebnet.it

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Summary

In this work we present an extension of Bell exponential polynomials to fractional and negative indices. This extension allows to calculate the fractional derivatives and fractional integrals of composite functions using the Faà di Bruno formula [8].

1. Introduction

The Bell exponential polynomials arise quite naturally from the differentiation of composite functions. They have been extensively studied [1,2] in the range of positive indices but they can be extended to negative and fractional indices as well. Bell exponential polynomials with fractional indices extend the classical method for obtaining the differentiation of composite functions to the case of fractional derivatives.

In the following text, we'll discuss this extension and its properties. As an application, we'll show an example of the utilization of Bell polynomials to calculate the integer and fractional derivatives of a specific composite function.

2. Review of Bell exponential polynomials for integer indices

$B_{n,k}(x_1, x_2 \dots x_{n-k+1})$ are homogeneous polynomials of degree k and weight n . The definition is

$$(1) \sum B_{n,k}(x_1, x_2 \dots x_{n-k+1}) = \sum \left(\frac{n!}{j_1! j_2! \dots j_{n-k+1}!} \left(\frac{x_1}{1!}\right)^{j_1} \left(\frac{x_2}{2!}\right)^{j_2} \dots \left(\frac{x_{n-k+1}}{(n-k+1)!}\right)^{j_{n-k+1}} \right)$$

Where the sum is over all j that are solutions to the system:

$$(2) \begin{cases} j_1 + j_2 + \dots + j_{n-k+1} = k \\ j_1 + 2j_2 + 3j_3 + \dots + (n-k+1)j_{n-k+1} = n \end{cases}$$

It's immediate to see that $B_{0,0} = 1$, $B_{0,k} = 0$ ($k \geq 1$) and $B_{n,n} = x_1^n$ (partition of one element into one block).

System (2) has $P(n-k)$ solutions, where $P(s)$ is the number of partitions of the integer $s=n-k$. Moreover, if we subtract the first equation from the second equation we obtain:

$$j_2 + 2j_3 + 3j_4 + \dots + sj_{s+1} = s$$

Or

$$j_I + 2j_{II} + 3j_{III} + \dots = s$$

The s coefficients j_I, j_{II}, \dots indicate how many times the numbers $1, 2, 3, \dots$ are taken when performing the partition. As an example, one partition of 5 is $3+1+1$; i.e. $j_I = 2, j_{II} = 1$ and all others $j = 0$.

This is always true for Bell polynomials having fractional indices; however, for those with integer indices some solutions can have coefficients divided by the factorial of a negative number and so those coefficients are null. These polynomials (with s integer) have $P(s)$ solutions only if $n \geq 2s$.

To obtain a general expression of these polynomials, we can start from the equation (1.3) of reference [3] or equation (5) of reference [4] i.e. :

$$B_{n,k} = \frac{1}{x_1} \frac{1}{n-k} \sum_{i=1}^{n-k} \binom{n}{i} \left[(k+1) - \frac{n+1}{i+1} \right] x_{i+1} B_{n-i,k} \quad n > k$$

Setting $k = n - 1$ we obtain

$$B_{n,n-1} = n \frac{n-1}{2} x_1^{n-2} x_2 \equiv \frac{n!}{(n-2)!} x_1^{n-2} \frac{x_2}{2}$$

In the same way, setting $k = n - 2$, we also obtain

$$B_{n,n-2} = n! \left[\frac{x_1^{n-3} x_3}{(n-3)! 3!} + \frac{x_1^{n-4} x_2^2}{(n-4)! 2^3} \right]$$

Similarly, setting $k = n - 3$

$$B_{n,n-3} = n! \left[\frac{x_1^{n-4} x_4}{(n-4)! 4!} + \frac{x_1^{n-5} x_2 x_3}{(n-5)! 2! * 3!} + \frac{x_1^{n-6} x_2^3}{(n-6)! 3! (2!)^3} \right]$$

And, in general

$$B_{n,n-s} = n! \left[\frac{x_1^{n-s-1} x_{s+1}}{(n-s-1)! (s+1)!} + \sum_{t=2}^s \frac{x_1^{n-s-t}}{(n-s-t)!} * \text{all the solutions of the system} \begin{cases} m_2 + m_3 + \dots + m_s = t \\ 2m_2 + 3m_3 + \dots + sm_s = s + t \end{cases} \right]$$

To make it explicit, the first eight formulas are listed in **Appendix 1**.

3. Extension to fractional and negative indices

The formulas discussed above can also be used for fractional and negative indices n, k , provided that the difference $s=n-k$ is positive or null. In the following, we present examples and discuss their properties and the range of possible j that are solution of system (2).

1) In general, when n or k (or both) are fractions in system (2), the number of solutions is infinite.

2) **Example: Investigation of the case where $n=4.5$ and $k=2.5$ and proof that it only has 2 solutions and leads to a Bell's polynomial**

Given $n=4.5$ and $k=2.5$, then $s=2$. We have

$$\begin{cases} j_1 + j_2 + j_3 = 2.5 \\ j_1 + 2j_2 + 3j_3 = 4.5 \end{cases}$$

Subtracting the first equation from the second equation we get:

$$j_2 + 2j_3 = 2$$

Assuming j_3 as a free parameter, we obtain Table A

	J_1	J_2	j_3
1)	1/2	2	0
2)	3/2	0	1
3)	5/2	-2	2
4)	1	1	1/2
5)	3/4	3/2	1/4
6)	2.9	-2.8	2.4
...)

This could go on and on.

However we can note that:

- The solutions j_i of the system cannot be negative integers because their factorial would be infinite. When n is a negative integer, one j (and only one) must be a negative integer.
- All the coefficients of Bell polynomials shown in Appendix 1 must be rational, as we can see noting that they are of the type $\frac{n!}{(n-t)!} \frac{1}{m}$ where m and t are integers¹.

The coefficients cannot be rational if

- t is not an integer (because of the term $\frac{n!}{(n-t)!}$)
- j_i is a fraction for $i > 1$

Moreover, from the definition (1) in section 2, we have

$$\left(\frac{1}{2!}\right)^{j_2} * \left(\frac{1}{3!}\right)^{j_3} \dots \left(\frac{1}{(s+1)!}\right)^{j_{s+1}}$$

The term 2^{j_2} is always present; when j_2 is not an integer, 2^{j_2} can be written in the form $\left(2^{\frac{1}{R}}\right)^T$ where R and T are integers. We notice that $2^{1/R}$ is irrational if $R > 1$; otherwise we would have $2 = \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^R$ i.e. $b^R + b^R = a^R$ (a and b are integers), and this is impossible due to the Fermat's last theorem, that states that the equation $a^R + b^R = c^R$ doesn't have integer solutions if $R > 2$. When $R = 2$, the square root of 2 is irrational.

Consequently, **in Table A only the solutions 1 and 2 are acceptable.**

It is worth noting that **in this example $s=n-k$ is 2 and the partitions of 2, $P(2)$, are just two.**

So the polynomial of our example is:

$$B_{4.5,2.5}(x_1, x_2, x_3) = 4.5! \left[\frac{x_1^{1.5} x_3}{1.5! 3!} + \frac{x_1^{0.5} x_2^2}{0.5! * 8} \right] = \frac{105}{16} x_1^{1.5} x_3 + \frac{945}{128} x_1^{0.5} x_2^2$$

¹ According to the well-known identity of Gamma function we have: $\frac{\Gamma(x+1)}{\Gamma(x)} = \frac{x!}{(x-1)!} = x$

For example

$$\frac{4.1!}{1.1!} = \frac{4.1!}{3.1!} * \frac{3.1!}{2.1!} * \frac{2.1!}{1.1!} = 4.1 * 3.1 * 2.1 = \frac{26691}{1000}$$

In fact, this polynomial is a Bell polynomial as it satisfies all the properties [1,5] of Bell polynomials:

- 1) $B_{n,k}(1,1,1,\dots,1) = \left\{ \begin{matrix} n \\ k \end{matrix} \right\}$ where $\left\{ \begin{matrix} n \\ k \end{matrix} \right\}$ is the Stirling number of second kind
 $B_{4.5,2.5}(1,1,1) = \frac{105}{16} + \frac{945}{128} = \frac{1785}{128} = 13.9453125$
- 2) $B_{n,k}(0!,1!,2!,3!,\dots,(n-k+1)!) = \left| \begin{matrix} n \\ k \end{matrix} \right|$ that is the Stirling numbers of first kind
 $B_{4.5,2.5}(1,1,2) = 2 \frac{105}{16} + \frac{945}{128} = \frac{2625}{128} = 20.5078125$

Note: Stirling numbers with fractional indices are quite new. They can be checked using the A. Labossière series [6,7] from which we have $\left\{ \begin{matrix} 4.5 \\ 2.5 \end{matrix} \right\} = \left| \begin{matrix} -2.5 \\ -4.5 \end{matrix} \right| = 13.9453125$ and $\left| \begin{matrix} 4.5 \\ 2.5 \end{matrix} \right| = 20.5078125$

- 3) $B(1,2,3,\dots,n-k+1) = \binom{n}{k} * k^{n-k}$ (idempotent number)
 $B_{4.5,2.5}(1,2,3) = \binom{4.5}{2.5} * 2.5^2 = \frac{1575}{32} = 49.21875$
i.e. $B_{4.5,2.5}(1,2,3) = 3 \frac{105}{16} + 4 \frac{945}{128} = 49.21875$
- 4) $B(1!,2!,3!,\dots,(n-k+1)!) = L(n,k)$ (Lah number = $\binom{n-1}{k-1} * \frac{n!}{k!}$) Type equation here.

See note²

In our case $\binom{3.5}{1.5} \frac{4.5!}{2.5!} = \frac{2205}{32}$

$$B_{4.5,2.5}(1,2,6) = \frac{105}{16} * 6 + \frac{945}{128} * 4 = \frac{2205}{32}$$

- 5) Recurrence relation $B_{n,k}(x_1, x_2, x_3 \dots x_{n-k+1}) = \sum_{i=1}^{n-k+1} \binom{n-1}{i-1} x_i B_{n-i,k-1}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n-k+1})$

This recurrence relation can be verified using the polynomials with $s=n-k=0, 1, 2$ (see Appendix 1)

$$B_{3.5,1.5} = \frac{35}{16} x_1^5 x_3 + \frac{105}{128} x_1^{-.5} x_2^2 \quad (\text{from Labossière series [6,7]}) \quad \left\{ \begin{matrix} 3.5 \\ 1.5 \end{matrix} \right\} = \frac{385}{128} = \frac{35}{16} + \frac{105}{128}$$

$$B_{2.5,1.5} = \frac{15}{8} x_1^5 x_2 \quad \left\{ \begin{matrix} 2.5 \\ 1.5 \end{matrix} \right\} = \frac{15}{8}$$

$$B_{1.5,1.5} = x_1^{1.5} \quad \left\{ \begin{matrix} 1.5 \\ 1.5 \end{matrix} \right\} = 1$$

So we have:

$$B_{4.5,2.5}(x_1, x_2, x_3) = x_1 \left(\frac{35}{16} x_1^5 x_3 + \frac{105}{128} x_1^{-.5} x_2^2 \right) + 3.5 x_2 \frac{15}{8} x_1^5 x_2 + \frac{35}{8} x_3 x_1^{1.5} = \frac{105}{16} x_1^{1.5} x_3 + \frac{945}{128} x_1^5 x_2^2$$

where we used: $\binom{3.5}{1} = 3.5$ $\binom{3.5}{2} = \frac{35}{2}$

3) **Other examples:** Similarly, for negative indices we can have:

$$B_{-2,-.5}(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = 105 x_1^{-8} x_2^3 - 60 x_1^{-7} x_2 x_3 + 5 x_1^{-6} x_4 \quad \text{or}$$

$$B_{-3.5,-.5}(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \frac{9009}{128} x_1^{-7.5} x_2^2 - \frac{231}{16} x_1^{-6.5} x_3$$

² More generally we have [5]

$$B_{n,k} = (1, 2! \binom{m}{1}, 3! \binom{m+1}{2}, 4! \binom{m+2}{3}, 5! \binom{m+3}{4}, \dots) = \binom{n}{k} \binom{mk+n-k-1}{n-k} (n-k)!$$

m can be a no integer number.

All these polynomials satisfy the five properties listed above.

It is possible to verify that all polynomials calculated by using the formulas reported in Appendix 1 satisfy the five properties listed above.

4. Application

As an application we illustrate the use of Bell exponential polynomials to obtain the integer or fractional derivatives of the composite function $h(x) = f(g(x))$

1) Integer indices

From Faà di Bruno's formula [8] we have

$$(3) \quad D^n h \equiv \frac{d^n h}{dx^n} = \sum_{k=1}^n f_k B_{n,k}(g_1, g_2, \dots, g_{n-k+1})$$

where

$$f_k = \frac{d^k f}{dg^k} \quad \text{i.e.} \quad f_1 = \frac{df}{dg}, f_2 = \frac{d^2 f}{dg^2} \quad \text{etc.}$$

$$g_k = \frac{d^k g}{dx^k} \quad \text{i.e.} \quad g_1 = \frac{dg}{dx}, g_2 = \frac{d^2 g}{dx^2} \quad \text{etc.}$$

A very simple example is:

Given $g(x) = 3x^2$ and $f = 2g^3(x)$, we know that

$$h(x) = 2 * (3x^2)^3 = 54x^6 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{d^2 h}{dx^2} = 1620x^4$$

Using Bell polynomials we have:

$$\frac{d^2 h}{dx^2} = \sum_{k=1}^2 f_k B_{2,k} = f_1 B_{2,1}(g_1, g_2) + f_2 B_{2,2}(g_1)$$

$$\text{and} \quad B_{2,1}(g_1, g_2) = g_2 \quad B_{2,2}(g_1) = g_1^2 \quad \text{and} \quad f_1 = 6g^2 \quad f_2 = 12g \quad g_1 = 6x \quad g_2 = 6 \quad g_3 = 0,$$

so we obtain

$$\frac{d^2 h}{dx^2} = 6g^2 g_2 + 12g g_1^2 = 6(3x^2)^2 6 + 12 * 3x^2 (6x)^2 = 1620x^4$$

2) Fractional indices

To obtain the fractional derivatives of composite functions, we can still use (3), but now we obtain a series of infinite terms as the sum is over all the possible polynomials, i.e. for k equal to $n, n-1, n-2, \dots$

An example will clarify the procedure.

Suppose we have $n=2.5$ and we want $\frac{d^{2.5} h}{dx^{2.5}}$ having, as before, $h=f(g(x))$ and $f=2g^3, g=3x^2$.

Obviously in this trivial case we can write directly: $h(x) = 54x^6$ and so

$$D^{2.5}(54x^6) = 54 \frac{6!}{3.5!} x^{3.5} = 3342.58148 \dots x^{3.5}$$

See note³

Alternatively, remembering that $D^{2.5}=D^{-5}D^2$ and $D^2 54x^6=1620x^4$, we can write

$$D^5(1620x^4) = 1620 \frac{4!}{3.5!} x^{3.5} = 3342.58148 x^{3.5}$$

To use the (3) we need:

$$B_{2.5,2.5} = g_1^{2.5}$$

$$B_{2.5,1.5} = \frac{15}{8} g_1^{.5} g_2$$

$$B_{2.5,0.5} = \frac{5}{16} g_1^{-.5} g_3 - \frac{15}{128} g_1^{-1.5} g_2^2$$

$$B_{2.5,-0.5} = \frac{-5}{128} g_1^{-1.5} g_4 + \frac{15}{128} g_1^{-2.5} g_2 g_3 - \frac{1875}{25600} g_1^{-3.5} g_2^3$$

where, being $g_3, g_4 = 0$, the equation is reduced to $\frac{-1875}{25600} g_1^{-3.5} g_2^3 = \frac{-1875}{25600\sqrt{6}} x^{-3.5} = -0.029901 x^{-3.5}$

We can calculate the terms for $k = -1.5, -2.5, \dots$

In similar way we have $\frac{d^{2.5}}{d^{2.5}} = \sum_{k=2.5,1.5,\dots} f_k B_{2.5,k}(g_1, g_2, \dots)$

In next Table B we list the first 13 terms of the series. Summing them all, we obtain 3342.58582, which is the exact answer to 6 significant digits.

k	f_k	$B_{2.5,k}$	Term of the series $*x^{3.5}$
2.5	23.45292 x^1	88.181630 $x^{2.5}$	2068.11678
1.5	46.90584 x^3	27.5567596 $x^{.5}$	1292.57294
0.5	56.28701 x^5	-0.2870496 $x^{-1.5}$	-16.15716
-0.5	48.24601 x^7	-0.0299010 $x^{-3.5}$	-1.4426037
-1.5	32.16400 x^9	-0.009811265 $x^{-5.5}$	-0.3155695
-2.5	17.54400 x^{11}	-0.00584587 $x^{-7.5}$	-0.1025601
-3.5	8.097232 x^{13}	-0.00517904 $x^{-9.5}$	-0.04191159
-4.5	3.2388928 x^{15}	-0.00614655 $x^{-11.5}$	-0.01990801
-5.5	1.1431386 x^{17}	-0.00920381 $x^{-13.5}$	-0.01052123
-6.5	0.3609911 x^{19}	-0.01668191 $x^{-15.5}$	-0.00602202
-7.5	0.1031403 x^{21}	-0.0355533 $x^{-17.5}$	-0.00366638
-8.5	0.0269061 x^{23}	-0.0871939 $x^{-19.5}$	-0.00234621
-9.5	0.0064574 x^{25}	-0.2420705 $x^{-21.5}$	-0.00156317

$$\sum_{k=2.5,1.5,\dots,-9.5} = 3342.58582$$

3) Fractional negative indices

It is worth noting that the formula

$$(3) D^n h \equiv \frac{d^n h}{d x^n} = \sum_{k=1}^n f_k B_{n,k}(g_1, g_2, \dots, g_{n-k+1})$$

³ In fractional calculus we have (a fractional number) $D^a x^k = \frac{k!}{(k-a)!} x^{k-a}$ and $I^a x^k = \frac{k!}{(k+a)!}$ When a is an integer number these relations become the usual calculus formula.

can also be used with a negative value of n , i.e. for integration (I^n operator).

Suppose that we have $n = -1/2$ and, as before, $h = f(g(x))$ and $f = 2g^3$, $g = 3x^2$

obviously, having $h = 54x^6$, $I^{1/2} h = 54 * \frac{6!}{6.5!} x^{6.5} = 20.7775 x^{6.5}$.

Using the (3) we have:

$$\frac{d^{-1/2}h}{dx^{-1/2}} \equiv I^{1/2} h = \sum_{k=-\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{3}{2}, -\frac{5}{2}, \dots} f_k * B_{-1/2, k}(g_1, g_2, g_3, \dots)$$

where

$$f_{-1/2} = I^{1/2} 2g^3 = 2 * \frac{3!}{3.5!} g^{3.5} = 1.03166 g^{3.5}$$

$$f_{-3/2} = I^{3/2} 2g^3 = 2 * \frac{3!}{4.5!} g^{4.5} = .229258 g^{4.5} \quad f_{-5/2} = 2 * \frac{3!}{5.5!} g^{5.5} = .041683 \quad \text{etc.}$$

and $g_1 = 6x$ $g_2 = 6$ $g_3 = 0$ and so on.

$$B_{-.5, -.5} = g_1^{-1/2} \quad B_{-.5, -1.5} = \frac{3}{8} g_1^{-2.5} g_2 \quad B_{-.5, -2.5}(g_1, g_2, g_3) = \frac{-5}{16} g_1^{-3.5} g_3 + \frac{105}{128} g_1^{-4.5} g_2^2 \quad \text{and so on.}$$

The first three terms of the series are:

$$1.03166 * (3x^2)^{3.5} * (6x)^{-0.5} + .229258 * (3x^2)^{4.5} * \frac{3}{8} (6x)^{-2.5} * 6 + .041683 * (3x^2)^{5.5} * \frac{105}{128} (6x)^{-4.5} * 6^2$$

$$= (19.696332 + .820681 + .1632026) x^{6.5} = 20.680216 x^{6.5}$$

Similarly, we can calculate the terms for $k = -3.5, -4.5$, up to $k = -10.5$ and we obtain $I^{1/2} h = 20.77682$.

*References

1. Bell polynomial Encyclopedia of Mathematics. Available at: [www.encyclopediaofmath.org/index.php?title=Bell polynomial](http://www.encyclopediaofmath.org/index.php?title=Bell_polynomial)
2. E. Bell. Exponential polynomials. Ann of Math 35 pp. 258-277 (1935)
3. Diurdje Cvijovic. New identities for partial Bell polynomials Appl. Math. Lett. 2U 1544-1547 (2011)
4. Stefen Egger. Identities for partial Bell polynomials derived from identities for weighted integer composition. Aequat: Math Springer Basel 2015 DOI 10.1007/s 00010-015-0338-2
5. Zhizheng Zhang and Jizhen Yang. Notes on Some Identities Related to the Partial Bell Polynomials. Tamsui Oxford Journal of Information and Mathem Sciences 28 (1) 2012 39-48
6. Labossiere André. OEIS Seq. A008275 (The on line Encyclopedia of integer sequences)
7. Numeri di Stirling (Wikipedia in Italian) Formula esplicita
8. Faà di Bruno formula. Available at [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Faà di Bruno %27S formula](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Faà_di_Bruno_%27S_formula)

Appendix 1

Exponential Bell Polynomials

$$B_{n,n} = x_1^n$$

$$B_{n,n-1} = \frac{n!}{(n-2)!} x_1^{n-2} \frac{x_2}{2!}$$

$$B_{n,n-2} = n! \left[\frac{x_1^{n-3}}{(n-3)!} \frac{x_3}{3!} + \frac{x_1^{n-4}}{(n-4)!} \frac{x_2^2}{2^3} \right]$$

$$B_{n,n-3} = n! \left[\frac{x_1^{n-4}}{(n-4)!} \frac{x_4}{4!} + \frac{x_1^{n-5}}{(n-5)!} \frac{x_2 x_3}{2! 3!} + \frac{x_1^{n-6}}{(n-6)!} \frac{x_2^3}{2^3 3!} \right]$$

$$B_{n,n-4} = n! \left[\frac{x_1^{n-5}}{(n-5)!} \frac{x_5}{5!} + \frac{x_1^{n-6}}{(n-6)!} \left(\frac{x_2 x_4}{2! 4!} + \frac{x_3^2}{3! 3! 2} \right) + \frac{x_1^{n-7}}{(n-7)!} \frac{x_2^2 x_3}{2^3 3!} + \frac{x_1^{n-8}}{(n-8)!} \frac{x_2^4}{2^4 4!} \right]$$

$$B_{n,n-5} = n! \left[\frac{x_1^{n-6}}{(n-6)!} \frac{x_6}{6!} + \frac{x_1^{n-7}}{(n-7)!} \left(\frac{x_2 x_5}{2! 5!} + \frac{x_3 x_4}{3! 4!} \right) + \frac{x_1^{n-8}}{(n-8)!} \left(\frac{x_2^2 x_4}{4! 2^3} + \frac{x_2 x_3^2}{3! 3! 2^2} \right) + \frac{x_1^{n-9}}{(n-9)!} \frac{x_2^3 x_3}{2^3 3! 3!} + \frac{x_1^{n-10}}{(n-10)!} \frac{x_2^5}{2^5 5!} \right]$$

$$B_{n,n-6} = n! \left[\frac{x_1^{n-7}}{(n-7)!} \frac{x_7}{7!} + \frac{x_1^{n-8}}{(n-8)!} \left(\frac{x_2 x_6}{2! 6!} + \frac{x_3 x_5}{3! 5!} + \frac{x_4^2}{4! 4! 2} \right) + \frac{x_1^{n-9}}{(n-9)!} \left(\frac{x_2^2 x_5}{2^3 5!} + \frac{x_2 x_3 x_4}{2! 3! 4!} + \frac{x_3^3}{3! 3! 3! 3!} \right) + \frac{x_1^{n-10}}{(n-10)!} \left(\frac{x_2^3 x_4}{2^3 3! 4!} + \frac{x_2^4 x_3}{2^4 3! 3!} + \frac{x_1^{n-11}}{(n-11)!} \frac{x_2^4 x_3}{2^4 3! 4!} + \frac{x_1^{n-12}}{(n-12)!} \frac{x_2^6}{2^6 6!} \right) \right]$$

$$B_{n,n-7} = n! \left[\frac{x_1^{n-8}}{(n-8)!} \frac{x_8}{8!} + \frac{x_1^{n-9}}{(n-9)!} \left(\frac{x_2 x_7}{2! 7!} + \frac{x_3 x_6}{3! 6!} + \frac{x_4 x_5}{4! 5!} \right) + \frac{x_1^{n-10}}{(n-10)!} \left(\frac{x_2^2 x_6}{2^3 6!} + \frac{x_2 x_3 x_5}{2! 3! 5!} + \frac{x_2 x_4^2}{2^2 4! 4!} + \frac{x_3^2 x_4}{2! 3! 4!} \right) + \frac{x_1^{n-11}}{(n-11)!} \left(\frac{x_2^3 x_5}{2^3 3! 5!} + \frac{x_2^2 x_3 x_4}{2^3 3! 4!} + \frac{x_2 x_3^3}{2 3! 3! 3!} \right) + \frac{x_1^{n-12}}{(n-12)!} \left(\frac{x_2^4 x_4}{2^4 4! 4!} + \frac{x_2^3 x_3^2}{2^4 3! 3! 3!} \right) + \frac{x_1^{n-13}}{(n-13)!} \frac{x_2^5 x_3}{2^5 3! 5!} + \frac{x_1^{n-14}}{(n-14)!} \frac{x_2^7}{2^7 7!} \right]$$

$$B_{n,n-8} = n! \left[\frac{x_1^{n-9}}{(n-9)!} \frac{x_9}{9!} + \frac{x_1^{n-10}}{(n-10)!} \left(\frac{x_8 x_2}{8! 2} + \frac{x_7 x_3}{7! 3!} + \frac{x_6 x_4}{6! 4!} + \frac{x_5^2}{2(5!)^2} \right) + \frac{x_1^{n-11}}{(n-11)!} \left(\frac{x_7 x_2^2}{7! (2!)^3} + \frac{x_6 x_3 x_2}{6! 3! 2!} + \frac{x_5 x_4 x_2}{5! 4! 2!} + \frac{x_5 x_3^2}{5! (3!)^2 2!} + \frac{x_4^2 x_3}{(4!)^2 3! 2!} \right) + \frac{x_1^{n-12}}{(n-12)!} \left(\frac{x_6 x_2^3}{6! 2^3 3!} + \frac{x_5 x_3 x_2^2}{5! 3! 2^2 2} + \frac{x_4 x_3^2 x_2}{4! (3!)^2 2^2} + \frac{x_4^2 x_2^2}{(4!)^2 2^4} + \frac{x_3^4}{(3!)^4 4!} \right) + \frac{x_1^{n-13}}{(n-13)!} \left(\frac{x_5 x_2^4}{5! (2!)^4 4!} + \frac{x_4 x_3 x_2^3}{4! 3! (2)^3 3!} + \frac{x_3^3 x_2^2}{(3!)^3 2^2 3! 2!} \right) + \frac{x_1^{n-14}}{(n-14)!} \left(\frac{x_4 x_2^5}{4! 2^5 5!} + \frac{x_3^2 x_2^4}{(3!)^2 2^4 2! 4!} \right) + \frac{x_1^{n-15}}{(n-15)!} \frac{x_3 x_2^6}{3! 2^6 6!} + \frac{x_1^{n-16}}{(n-16)!} \frac{x_2^8}{2^8 8!} \right]$$